

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

The role of organizational commitment in mediating the effect of job satisfaction on organizational citizenship behavior and performance

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine the role of organizational commitment in mediating the effect of job satisfaction on organizational citizenship behavior and the performance of members of the National Police at the Kendari Police. Data collection is done by using questionnaires and documentation. The population of this research is all members of the Kendari Police as many as 800 members, then sampling and producing as many as 89 members. The analytical tool used is SmartPLS 3. The results showed that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment at the Kendari Police, Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior at the Kendari Police, Job satisfaction has a positive and insignificant effect on performance at the Kendari Police, organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior at the Kendari Police, organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Kendari Police, organizational commitment plays a role in mediating the effect of job satisfaction on organizational citizenship behavior at the Kendari Police, organizational commitment plays a role in mediating the effect of job satisfaction on performance at the Kendari Police.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction; Organizational Commitment; Organizational Citizenship Behavior; Performance

1. Introduction

Police Country Republic Indonesia is wrong one organization government whose function is to maintain security and order in the middle community beside that also on duty in to do investigation against criminal matters. Definition of policing according to the Police Act Republic of Indonesia Number 28 of 1997 chapter 1 and Law Republic of Indonesia Police Number 2 of 2002 chapter 1 is all things which related with function and institution police in accordance with regulation laws and regulations of the Indonesian National Police. State Police Republic Indonesia carry tasks police throughout region Indonesia. POLRI is tool country which responsible answer in carry out internal security, including carrying out Duty tree as maintenance security and order Public, upholding the law as well as protecting, nurturing and serving the community. Polri as mandated in Chapter 13 Law No 2 Year 2002 has main tasks which include among others maintaining security and order Public, enforce law, and give protection, protection and service to Public.

To assess police activities and performance, and how and where to source power must applied, needed matrix performance which objective (1). As a government-owned organization that provides services to the community, in this case the Polri organization, of course, must always be adept in every action which conducted based on law which apply. In To improve performance, of course, it requires the help of fellow members as well creation performance which good no regardless from exists satisfaction as well as commitment from member that alone. Job satisfaction is basically a

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sense of security (security feeling) and has a socio-economic aspect such as salary and social security, as well as a social aspect psychology like opportunity for Up, opportunity getting awards, dealing with supervisory issues, dealing with association Among employee with employee and Among employee with superiors (2). (3), describe work satisfaction as "a pleasant or upbeat emotional state due to evaluation work or experience work".

(4) explain job satisfaction is a state positive emotions that are the result of evaluating work experiences somebody. Work satisfaction that considered as results from experience employees in relation to their own values as desired and expected of his job. Two theory work satisfaction which most organized associated with (5) and (6). Creation Maslow focus on what which is often referred to as the "needs hierarchy" with that main premise needs level low (physiological, security, and flavor have) need fulfilled before individual could Fulfill needs level tall they (appreciation and self-actualization). This hierarchical model assumes that when low-level needs are not met, they occupy the individual's attention and obstruct attention on needs level which more tall. Behavior individual motivated by desire for satisfying needs which most important on point or period time certain. Work satisfaction which tall capable push organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior, and performance. Work satisfaction from member organizations strongly encourage their commitment to the organization, in a study explain that work satisfaction which tall increase in a manner significant organizational commitment, (7-14).

Organizational commitment is described by (15) as exchange relationship each party creates demands specific to other party while giving something in return. Party contributions employee depicted in two form general, production and participation. (16) argue that, though there is enhancement attention for studies commitment in the place work, still there is confusion and disagreement about what commitment that, to where that directed and how it develops and influences behavior. (17) that commitment is not only related to level go out entry employee, but also related with level willingness employee for sacrifice for company.

Based on study (7), (10), (18), (14) showing that organizational commitment take effect positive and significant to organizational citizenship behavior, Thing this prove that the higher the organizational commitment it will significantly increase organizational citizenship behavior, and vice versa (19). Research results by (9), (11), (20), (21) organizational commitment has a significant effect on performance of brand research results indicate that the higher the organizational commitmental performance will increase and the level of commitment will be low will have an impact on decreasing the level of performance (22), and (23).

In addition to a direct relationship, organizational commitment plays a role mediation influence work satisfaction to performance as findings research by (7), (10), (18) in their research findings show that organizational commitment role as mediation influence work satisfaction to organizational citizenship behavior, while research findings by Widyanto, Lau, And Kartika (2013) showing that organizational commitment no role as mediation influence influence work satisfaction to organizational citizenship behavior. In addition, organizational commitment acts as a mediation of job satisfaction on performance. (9) work satisfaction take effect positive and significant to performance through organizational commitment, meanwhile results of research conducted by (11), (23) shows that organizational commitment does not play a role in mediate influence work satisfaction to performance.

According to (24), structure formal not enough and far from perfection, and cooperation are the most important requirements of the organization which must complement the formal structure for an effective work environment. (25) noticed that organizations need cooperation to work in a manner efficient and effective and state that "a organization which relying only on blueprints for defined behavior is the system fragile society" (25) that will break down. OCB is inevitable for a organization to survive. Katz appreciated its importance action beyond the line of duty prior to (26) conceptualization of behavior citizenship organization (OCB). (27) Organizational Citizenship Behavior is contribution individual in exceed demands role in place work. OCB this include some behaviors include helping people behavior others, volunteering for extra tasks, obeying the rules and procedures at work. (28). Organizational Citizenship Behavior(OCB) as something behavior individual which characteristic free (discretionary), which no in a manner direct and explicit get hope from system return information which overall push functions organization.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

2.1. Job satisfaction

By (29) Job satisfaction is a happy emotional state or emotion positive which originated from evaluation profession or experience work someone then (4) explained work satisfaction is circumstances emotional which positive which is results from evaluation experience work somebody. Work satisfaction that considered as results from experience employee in relationship with score alone what you want and expect from your job. This view can be simplified that job

satisfaction is attitude from individual and is built back against his job. (30) and (31) Work satisfaction as circumstances emotion pleasant or positive which generated employee from evaluation profession or experience work.

In study this for measure work satisfaction police personnel, researchers refer to the indicators or dimensions measuring satisfaction that work stated by (29), namely:

- That job alone
- Wages
- Promotion
- Supervision superior
- Group work
- Condition work

2.2. Organizational Commitment

Build organizational commitment very important in all organization, because organizational commitment give role important in success an organization, police officers or employee which have commitment which good have performance or results work which good. Organizational commitment is described by (15) as exchange relationship each party creates demands specific to other party while giving something in return. (17), formulate something definition about commitment in organize as a psychological construct which is characteristics of the relationship between members of the organization with the organization and have implication to decision individual to continue membership in organize. In line with the theory expressed by (29), argues that organizational commitment is an attitude that reflects loyalty employee on organization and process sustainable where member organization express attention to organization and success and continuous progress.

In this study to measure organizational commitment using indicator which put forward by (17), share organizational commitment be three type on the basic source is:

- Affective Commitment, related to being emotionally related to organization, identity and engagement based on shared values same
- Continuance Commitment, commitment based on awareness of costs which will borne if no join organized. Here also based on by no exists alternatives other.
- Normative Commitment, a commitment based on a feeling of obligation as a employees to stay because of feelings of indebtedness. Here it happened also internalisation norms.

2.3. Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Organizational citizenship behavior showing behavior score plus which there is on self employee or employee one form Act in demand prosocial, ie Act in demand social which positive, constructive and each other help to fellow. (32) Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) is contribution worker "on and more from" description work formal. could interpreted that organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) involves several behavioral things which include helping behavior person other, Becomes volunteer for tasks additionally, comply rules and on-site procedures work. In line with the opinion expressed by (33) suggested that OCB as behavior discretionary which aim for increase destination organization with involve employee in action volunteer based on choice personnel them than requirements profession Required and obligation contract. Activity volunteer consists from behavior social which positive and constructive includes a willingness to complete tasks without consider time or inconveniences personnel or help colleague work other without expect benefit in future. (34) Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) as behavior individual who free, no related in a manner direct or explicit with system rewards and can increase effective function organization.

For measure *Organization citizenship behavior* in study this refer on indicator which put forward by (35), ie as following

- Altruism
- Courtesy
- Sportsmanship
- Conscientiousness
- civics virtue

2.4. Performance

Performance is the result of work achieved by each member of the National Police in work units/functional units/regional units in accordance with generic factors, (Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia National Police Number 2 of 2018 article 1:2). This is in line with the theory put forward by (36), performance is achievement somebody or

organization to achieve purpose . In line with the previous opinion, (37) argues that performance is a record of the results produced (produced) on function profession certain or activities During period certain. Definition performance as results also related with productivity and effectiveness. Then (38), performance interpreted willingness somebody or group people to do something activity, and perfect it in accordance responsibility with results like which expected. (39), performance is a measure that includes effectiveness and efficiency. Effective related with achievement target, currently efficient is ratio Among output which effective with inputs required for reach target.

In study this for measure performance member police, researcher refers to the Regulation of the State Police of the Republic of Indonesia Number 2 Year 2018 chapter 15 (2) about evaluation performance member police Republic of Indonesia with a behavior management system. Personnel behavior is every behavior, attitude or action carried out by members of the Police or no To do something which should conducted in accordance with statutory provisions. The dimensions of member performance appraisal include:

- Leadership
- Service Orientation
- Communication
- Emotional Control
- Integrity, Empathy
- Commitment To Organization
- Initiative
- Discipline
- Cooperation

From the literature review. The conceptual framework of this study is shown below:

Figure 1 Research Conceptual Framework

Based on the conceptual framework in the picture above, the hypothesis proposed in this study is as follows:

- Hypothesis 1. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the organizational commitment of Polri members at the Kendari Police Station.
- Hypothesis 2. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior of Polri members at the Kendari Police Station.
- Hypothesis 3. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Polri members at the Kendari Police Station.
- Hypothesis 4. Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior of Polri members at the Kendari Police Station.
- Hypothesis 5. Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Polri members at the Kendari Police Station.
- Hypothesis 6. Organizational commitment acts as a mediating effect of Job Satisfaction on organizational citizenship behavior of Polri members at the Kendari Police Station

- Hypothesis 7. Organizational commitment plays a role in mediating the effect of job satisfaction on the performance of Polri members at the Kendari Police Station

3. Methods

The purpose of this study was to examine the role of organizational commitment in mediating the effect of job satisfaction on organizational citizenship behavior and the performance of members of the National Police at the Kendari Police. The population of this research is all members of the Kendari Police as many as 800 members, then sampling and producing as many as 89 members. Measurement of data in this study using a Likert scale . In data processing, the Likert scale is included in the interval scale, the determination of the Likert scale of this study is made on a scale of 1 to 5. The guideline for measuring all variables is to use 5 points, where if there is an answer with a low weight then a score of 1 is given and so on so that the answer with a high weight is given a score of 5. This research data was tested using SmartPLS 3.0 software.

4. Results

4.1. Characteristics of Respondents

Respondents included in this study were members of the traffic police at the Kendari Police, totaling 89 people. The description of the characteristics of the respondents in this study aims to explain the characteristics of Kendari Police which include age, gender, years of service, rank and income which are shown in table 1 below:

Table 1 Characteristics Respondents

No	Characteristics Respondents	Frequency (person)	Percentage (%)	
1	Age (Year)	21-30	19	21.3
		31-40	41	46.1
		41-49	29	32.6
		Amount	89	100
2	Gender	Man	61	68.5
		Woman	28	31.5
		Amount	89	100
3	Years of service (Year)	3-5	3	3.4
		5-10	16	18.0
		11-15	13	14.6
		16-20	25	28.1
		21-25	28	31.5
		26-29	4	4.5
Amount	89	100		
4	Rank	BRIGADIER	3	3.4
		BRIPDA	3	3.4
		BRIPTU	16	18.0
		BRIGPOL	1	1.1
		BRIFKA	27	30.3
		AIPDA	22	24.7

		AIPTU	5	5.6
		IPDA	7	7.9
		IPTU	2	2.2
		AKP	2	2.2
		KOMPOL	1	1.1
		Amount	89	100
5	Income (Rupiah)	2-5 Million	37	41.6
		6-10 Million	50	56.2
		11 Million	1	1.1
		25 Million	1	1.1
		Amount	89	100

Data source Primary processed, year 2022

4.2. Convergent validity

Table 2 Results *Outer Loadings* Variable Study

Variable Study	Dimensions/Items Variable	Original sample (O)	Q Statistics (O/stddev)	P Value
Work Satisfaction	X.1.1	0.695	10,723	0.000
	X.1.2	0.708	5,768	0.000
	X.2.1	0.895	30,203	0.000
	X.2.2	0.856	26,512	0.000
	X.3.1	0.750	8,260	0.000
	X.3.2	0.853	21,643	0.000
	X.4.1	0.866	16,138	0.000
	X.4.2	0.875	19,346	0.000
	X.5.1	0.869	23,525	0.000
	X.5.2	0.726	6,244	0.000
	X.6.1	0.644	6,875	0.000
	X.6.2	0.737	11,375	0.000
Organization Commitment	Y1.1.1	0.646	7,754	0.000
	Y1.1.2	0.784	13,352	0.000
	Y1.1.3	0.624	6,427	0.000
	Y1.2.1	0.597	5,021	0.000
	Y1.2.2	0.801	16,595	0.000
	Y1.3.1	0.827	17,840	0.000
	Y1.3.2	0.721	10,573	0.000
	Y1.3.3	0.679	7,120	0.000
	Y2.1.1	0.787	16,720	0.000

Organizational Citizenship Behavior	Y2.1.2	0.645	11,200	0.000
	Y2.2.1	0.685	7,302	0.000
	Y2.2.2	0.789	15,695	0.000
	Y2.3.1	0.790	14,480	0.000
	Y2.3.2	0.814	20,744	0.000
	Y2.4.1	0.816	15,037	0.000
	Y2.4.2	0.755	11,798	0.000
	Y2.5.1	0.661	1,108	0.000
	Y2.5.2	0.618	5,740	0.000
Performance	Y3.1	0.847	25,695	0.000
	Y3.2	0.850	25,379	0.000
	Y3.3	0.911	30,398	0.000
	Y3.4	0.824	15,065	0.000
	Y3.5	0.528	4,500	0.000
	Y3.6	0.842	19,402	0.000
	Y3.7	0.807	13,153	0.000
	Y3.8	0.831	13,651	0.000
	Y3.9	0.713	9,796	0.000
	Y3.10	0.841	17,060	0.000

Sumber: Data Primer Diolah, Tahun 2022

Based on table 2 above can see results outer loadings that measurement of job satisfaction as many as 12 dimension items, organizational commitment 10 dimensional items, organizational citizenship behavior 10 dimensional items, and 10 performance items dimensions in a manner whole is valid for used in reflects the measurement of job satisfaction, organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior, and performance.

4.3 Discriminant Validity

The next evaluation is by comparing the AVE root value with the correlation between constructs. The recommended result is that the AVE root value should be higher than the correlation between constructs. The model has better discriminant validity if the square root of the AVE for each construct is greater than the correlation between the constructs in the model.

Table 3 Latent Variable Correlation

Variabel Penelitian	Correlation			
	X	Y1	Y2	Y3
Work Satisfaction	100			
Organizational Commitment	0.744	100		
Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.739	0.776	100	
Performance	0.669	0.817	840	100

Source: Data processed, Year 2022

Based on the table, it can be seen that the AVE root value for each variable is greater than the correlation value so that the construct in this research model can still be said to have good discriminant validity. On the basis of this, it is concluded that all indicators and variables are valid and meet the requirements of discriminant validity .

4.3. Research Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is carried out to answer the problems posed in this study with the results of data analysis carried out. Hypothesis testing was carried out according to the research framework carried out to analyze and test directly and indirectly between exogenous and endogenous variables with a mediation model.

Figure 2 Results of Data Analysis Using SmartPLS

4.3.1 Direct Effect Test

Hypothesis testing is done by looking at the output path coefficient from the bootstrap resampling results as follows:

Table 4 Results of Direct Hypothesis Testing

Influence Between Variables	Original Sample	P Values	Note
Work Satisfaction → Organization Commitment	0.744	0.000	Accepted
Work Satisfaction → OCB	0.362	0.000	Accepted
Work Satisfaction → kinerja	0.138	0.260	Rejected
Organization Commitment → OCB	0.507	0.000	Accepted
Organization Commitment → Performance	0.714	0.038	Accepted

Source: Data Processed 2022

4.3.2 Indirect Effect Test

The test of job satisfaction on OCB and performance through organizational commitment. The results of the analysis of this research can be explained as follows:

Table 5 Indirect Hypothesis Testing Results

Influence Between Variables	P Values	Note
Work Satisfaction → Organization Commitment → OCB	0.007	Accepted
Work Satisfaction → Organization Commitment → Performance	0.020	Accepted

Source: Data Processed 2022

5. Discussion

5.1. The Effect of Work Satisfaction On Organizational Commitments

Results testing work satisfaction to organization commitment produces an *estimated* path coefficient value of 0.744 in a positive direction. Coefficient track with sign positive have meaning influence work satisfaction towards organizational commitment is in the same direction as evidenced by values significant (*sig.t*) of $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. Thus the test results the hypothesis proves that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect to organizational commitment could received. With thereby could concluded that hypothesis first which submit in study this acceptable. Findings This study indicates that with increasing satisfaction the work of members of the Kendari Police Police will increase the level of commitment their organization at the Kendari police station. Job satisfaction is a response emotional to situation work as well as level in where member satisfied or fulfilled by the work done with the dimensions of the work itself, salaries, promotions, supervisor supervision, work groups, and working conditions. whereas Organizational commitment is a behavior of Polri members in the organization which related with trust and reception which strong on destination and values organization, exists will for try achievement interest organization, and desire for maintain position as a member of the organization in this case will remain in the organization with the dimensions of *affective commitment*, *continuance commitment*, and *normative commitment*.

Someone who has good job satisfaction will make people have a high commitment and will remain in the organization the. Findings study this support study (7), (8), (9), (10), (11), (12), (13), (23), and (14) findings study they showing that work satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment.

5.2. The Effect of Work Satisfaction To organizational Citizenship Behavior

Results testing work satisfaction to organizational citizenship behavior produces an estimated path coefficient value of 0.362 with direction positive. The path coefficient with a positive sign means the effect of job satisfaction to organizational citizenship behavior is in the same direction. Next if seen from the probability value (Sig. t) of $0.006 < \alpha = 0.05$. Test result hypothesis proven that work satisfaction take effect significant to organizational citizenship behavior, so could said hypothesis second which filed in study this could received. The findings of this study indicate that job satisfaction is job satisfaction positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior . This means that the increase in the work itself, salary, promotion, supervisor supervision, work groups, and working conditions significantly increase altruism, courtesy, sportsmanship, conscientiousness, and civic virtue. The findings of this study support the research of (7), (10), (18) findings study they showing that work satisfaction take effect positive and significant to organizational citizenship behavior, meaning that the more good level satisfaction in something organization so will the more increase organizational citizenship behavior,

5.3. The Effect of Work Satisfaction To Performance

Based on results testing work satisfaction to performance produces an *estimated* path coefficient value of 0.138 in a positive direction. Coefficient track with sign positive have meaning influence work satisfaction to performance is in the same direction, whereas if seen from score significant $0.260 > \alpha = 0.05$ which means that job satisfaction has no significant positive effect on performance, thus it can be concluded that the third hypothesis in this research rejected. Results study this showing that work satisfaction take effect positive no significant to performance, it means that study this indicates that job satisfaction does not make a significant contribution to enhancement performance, Thing this caused by low level work satisfaction of members of the Kendari Police Police as reflected in work itself, salary, promotion, supervisor supervision, work group, and working conditions whereas performance reflected with leadership, orientation service, communication, control emotional, integrity, empathy, commitment to organization, initiative, discipline, and cooperation. The findings of this study indicate that job satisfaction has an effect positive no significant to performance so that findings study this supports the research findings of (40) which show that job satisfaction has no significant effect on performance. On the other hand findings study no in line findings (22), (20), (41), (21), (23) showing that organizational commitment take effect positive and significant on performance, meaning that the better the level of organizational commitment in an organization that has employees will further improve performance.

5.4. The Effect Of Organizational Commitment On Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Results of testing organizational commitment to organizational citizenship behavior produces an estimated path coefficient value of 0.507 with direction positive. Coefficient track with sign positive have meaning influence organizational commitment to organizational citizenship behavior is in the same direction. Next if seen from the probability value (Sig. t) as big $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. Results testing hypothesis proven that organizational commitment take effect positive and significant to organizational citizenship behavior. It means increasing organizational commitment in

the direction of improvement organizational citizenship behavior, so that it can be said the fourth hypothesis proposed in this research could be received. Results study this showing that organizational commitment which reflected with affective, commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment take effect positive and significant to organizational citizenship behavior that is reflected in altruism, courtesy, sportsmanship, conscientiousness, and civic virtue. It means that enhancement organizational commitment in a manner significant increase organizational citizenship behavior, and vice versa if organizational commitment decreases then organizational citizenship behavior will significantly decrease. The research findings strengthen the findings of (7), (10), (18), and (14) in their research findings show that organizational commitment positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior, meaning that the higher the organizational commitment possessed by workers it will further increase organizational citizenship behavior.

5.5. The Effect of Organizational Commitment on Performance

Based on results testing organization commitment to performance produces an *estimated* path coefficient value of 0.714 in a positive direction. The path coefficient with a positive sign means the influence of organizational commitment on performance is unidirectional as evidenced by a significant value (sig.t) as big $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. Results testing hypothesis prove that organizational commitment take effect positive and significant significant to performance is acceptable, so the fifth hypothesis is proposed could be received. Results study this showing that organizational commitment which reflected with affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment has a positive and significant effect on performance reflected with leadership, orientation service, communication, control emotional, integrity, empathy, commitment to organization, initiative, discipline, and cooperation. This means that the increase in organizational commitment in a manner significant increase performance, thereby on the contrary if organizational commitment decreased then performance in a manner significant will experience decline. This research supports the findings of (9), (11), (20), and (21) in findings their research shows that organizational commitment has a positive effect and significant to performance, it means that the more tall organizational commitment owned by workers will further improve performance.

5.6. The Effect Of Work Satisfaction To Organizational Citizenship Behavior Through Organizational Commitment As Mediation

The results of the evaluation of testing the role of organizational commitment in mediating the influence of job satisfaction on organizational citizenship behavior, in a way direct job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment, job satisfaction has a positive and significant direct effect to organizational citizenship behavior and organizational commitment in a manner direct positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior. With thereby organizational commitment in model study this play a role in mediating the effect of job satisfaction on organizational citizenship behavior this is evidenced by the path coefficient value of 0.377 with significance level of $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. Based on these results show that in a manner direct work satisfaction could increase organizational citizenship behavior nor through enhancement organizational commitment, so that could said that hypothesis sixth which filed in study could be received. Based on the results of this study indicate that organizational commitment play a role in mediating the effect of job satisfaction on organizational citizenship behavior of members of the Kendari Police. The role of organizational commitment in mediate influence work satisfaction to organizational citizenship behavior is known that direct work satisfaction take effect positive and significant to organizational commitment, work satisfaction in a manner direct positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior, and organizational commitment direct effect positive and significant to organizational citizenship behavior. With thereby organizational commitment in model study this role in mediate influence work satisfaction to performance with properties mediation part. The findings of this study support the research of (7), (10), (18) in research they showing that organizational commitment role as mediation the effect of job satisfaction on organizational citizenship behavior, meaning that in enhancement organizational citizenship behavior can be conducted in a manner direct with increase papacy work nor through organizational commitment.

5.7. The Effect Of Work Satisfaction To Performance Through Organizational commitment As Mediation

The results of the evaluation of testing the role of organizational commitment in mediating influence work satisfaction to performance, in a manner direct work satisfaction positive and significant effect on organizational commitment, job satisfaction in a manner direct take effect positive no significant to performance and organizational commitment in a manner direct take effect positive and significant on performance. Thus organizational commitment in the research model this plays a role in mediating the effect of job satisfaction on the performance of this matter proven score coefficient track as big 0.531 with level significant $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. Based on these results indicate directly job satisfaction not proven to increase performance, performance improvement can be done through role organizational

commitment, so that nature mediation in research as mediation full. With thereby could said that hypothesis heading which filed in research can received.

Based on the results of this study indicate that organizational commitment play a role in mediating the effect of job satisfaction on member performance Polres Kendari. Role organizational commitment in mediate influence work satisfaction to performance is known that in a manner direct Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment, work satisfaction directly has no significant positive effect on performance and organizational commitment in a manner direct take effect positive and significant on performance. Thus organizational commitment in the research model this plays a role in mediating the effect of job satisfaction on performance with nature mediation full. Study this support findings study (9), in research findings explain that organizational commitment can mediate the effect of job satisfaction on performance, meaning that organizational commitment which tall could becomes mediation work satisfaction in improve the performance.

6. Conclusion

Based on results and discussion in study this, so could put forward a number of The conclusion is Work satisfaction positive effect and significant to commitment members of the Indonesian National Police at the Kendari Police. Work satisfaction take effect positive and significant to organizational citizenship behavior of Polri members to the Kendari Police. Work satisfaction take effect positive no significant to performance members of the Police at the Kendari Police. Organizational commitment take effect positive and significant to organizational citizenship behavior of Polri members to the Kendari Police. Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on performance members of the Police at the Kendari Police. Organization commitment role in mediate influence work satisfaction to organizational citizenship behavior member Police on Polres Kendari. It means that enhancement organizational citizenship behavior can conducted with increase work satisfaction as well as through role organizational commitment. Organizational commitment role in mediate influence work satisfaction to performance member Police on Polres Kendari. In In this study, the nature of mediation is full mediation, meaning that work satisfaction directly does not have a significant effect on performance, and Organizational commitment acts as a mediating effect of job satisfaction to performance

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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